

Cassia fistula Linn. :

Air dried and powdered flowers of *C. fistula* (1 kg), collected from Midnapore district of West Bengal in May were extracted in a Soxhlet apparatus for 40 h each with petroleum ether and chloroform successively. The petroleum ether extract on concentration and cooling deposited a solid which was separated by filtration. Chromatography of the solid over a silica gel column gave aurantiamide acetate (eluate : chloroform-methanol, 49 : 1) and that of the concentrate of the filtrate gave CF-1, an uncharacterised fatty acid ester of β -sitosterol (petroleum ether-benzene, 1 : 1), and β -sitosterol (benzene). The concentrate of the chloroform extract on column chromatography over silica gel afforded a further amount of aurantiamide acetate along with β -sitosterol- β -D-glucoside (chloroform-methanol, 9 : 1).

Aurantiamide acetate, a modified phenylalanine dipeptide, crystallising from chloroform-petroleum ether as clusters of hairy needles, m.p. 185° (lit¹⁶, 185°), $[\alpha]_D^{25} -44^\circ$ (c 0.12 in CHCl₃), was identified from its spectral properties and finally by direct comparison with an authentic sample¹⁶. The ir spectrum of CF-1 indicated the presence of an ester C=O (1735 cm⁻¹) and its ¹H nmr spectrum exhibited signals at δ 1.22 (~24H, s), 2.23 (2H, t, J 6 Hz) and 4.3-4.7 (1H, m). Its hydrolysis with ethanolic 1N HCl afforded β -sitosterol. Thus, CF-1 appeared to be an ester of β -sitosterol and a fatty acid. It could not be characterised owing to paucity of material.

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Chemical Investigation of *Alstonia congensis* Engl.—Isolation of Rhazine

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THE major source of indole alkaloids in nature are plants belonging to different genera of the family Apocynaceae. Several species of the genus *Alstonia* (family: Apocynaceae) occur widely in tropical countries of Asia and Africa. The extract of different species of this genus are reputed as antimalarials and in many cases as a tonic for general debility. In the present communication we report the systematic investigation of the stem-bark of *Alstonia congensis* and the characterisation of one of the constituent alkaloids as rhazine¹ (1).

Sun-dried stem-bark of *Alstonia congensis* (collected from Africa) was powdered, defatted with petrol and then extracted with methanol at room temperature for 20 days. The concentrated methanolic extract was churned with aqueous 5% citric acid solution and the mixture filtered. The aqueous extract was basified with NH₃ solution at 0° to pH 9 and extracted with chloroform. The concentrated chloroform extract was chromatographed over alumina. An alkaloid, C₂₁H₂₄N₂O₃ (M⁺ 352), m.p. 235-36° d, was obtained from the benzene-chloroform (1 : 1) eluates. Its mass spectrum showed prominent peaks at *m/z* 352 (M⁺), 351 (M-1), 337 (M-CH₃), 321 (M-OCH₃/CH₂OH), 170, 169, 168 and 154, respectively. The latter fragments are characteristic of the tetrahydro- β -carboline moiety. Its uv spectrum further corroborated this view, showing λ_{max} at 291, 280-283 and 227 nm (log ϵ 3.78, 3.87 and 4.52) which suffered a hypsochromic shift to 290, 273-274 and 222 nm (log ϵ 3.81, 3.93 and 4.56) in presence of a trace of acid. It showed ir bands at 3150-3400 (br, OH), 1705 and 1215 (ester C=O), 1445, 840 and 730 cm⁻¹, respectively. The spectroscopical data (uv, ir, ms, ¹H nmr) indicated that the alkaloid was probably identical with rhazine¹.

Finally its identity was established as rhazine by direct comparison (m.m.p., co-tlc and superimposable ir) with an authentic sample. The complete ^1H nmr assignment of rhazine, which to our knowledge has not been reported so far is given here. 200 MHz ^1H nmr (recorded in CDCl_3 on a Bruker WP-200) δ 1.66 (3H, dd, J 6.7 and 1.9 Hz, C(18)H); 1.70-2.05 (3H, br m, C(14)H₂ and OH); 2.70 (1H, ddd, J 13, 4.3 and 1.9 Hz, C(15)H); 2.95 (3H, s, CO₂CH₃), 3.31 (1H, dd, J 15.5 and 1.6 Hz, C(6)H); 3.00-3.12 (2H, m, C(5)H and C(6)H); 3.60-3.62 (2H, br, CH₂OH); 3.69 and 3.84 (AB-system each of 1H, d, J 10.5 Hz, N-C(21)H₂); 4.31 (1H, dd, J 10.4 and 0.8 Hz, C(3)H); 5.41 (1H, br q, J 6.7 Hz, C(19)H); 7.06 (1H, dt, J_o 7.0, J_m 1.5 Hz, C(10)H); 7.13 (1H, dt, J_o 7.0, J_m 1.5 Hz, C(11)H); 7.30 (1H, br dd, J_m 1.5 Hz, partially obscured by CHCl_3 signal, C(12)H); 7.44 (1H, br dd, J_o 8.6, J_m 1.5 Hz, C(9)H) and 7.98 (1H, br s, NH).

The concentrate of the benzene eluate afforded a non-alkaloidal compound, m.p. 184-85°, as white granules. It showed characteristic bands at 3 300-3 500 (br) for hydroxyl group in the ir spectrum. The spectroscopical data (uv, ir, ms) indicated that the compound was an aliphatic diol, C₂₈H₃₄O₇ (M^+ 426). A number of other alkaloidal components have been isolated. These are being characterised.

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A New Flavonol Glycoside from the Mature Tubers of *Cyperus rotundus* L.

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WE have previously reported¹ a new saponin from mature tubers of *Cyperus rotundus* L. We now report the isolation of a flavonol glycoside (1)

C₂₈H₃₄O₇, m.p. 196° d from the same source. This glycoside has not been isolated earlier from any plant source.

1 on acid hydrolysis gave an aglycone and rhamnose. The aglycone C₁₆H₁₂O₇, m.p. 284° gave all characteristic colour reactions of a flavonol² and was identified as rhamnetin on the basis of uv, ir, nmr and mass fragmentation pattern and con-chromatography with an authentic sample.

Methylation of 1 followed by acid hydrolysis gave 5,7,3',4'-tetramethoxyquercetin confirming the attachment of sugar at 3-position. The glycoside was fully methylated, hydrolysed and the resulting partially methylated sugars were identified as 2,3-di-O-methylrhamnose and 2,3,4-tri-O-methylrhamnose^{3,4}. This established the glycoside as a (1→4) trioside of rhamnose linked at 3-position of the aglycone. On this basis, 1 was identified as rhamnetin 3-O-rhamnosyl (1→4) rhamnopyranoside.

Experimental

The tubers of *Cyperus rotundus* L. were extracted with ethanol, concentrated and extracted with ether and ethyl acetate, respectively. Extraction with ethyl acetate and chromatography over silica gel with C₆H₆-EtOAc (1:1) gave 1, m.p. 196° d (EtOH); λ_{max} (EtOH) 255 and 355; (AlCl₃) 260 and 400; (AlCl₃-HCl) 270 and 400; (NaOAc) 255; (NaOAc/H₃BO₃) 260 and 390 nm.

On hydrolysis, 1 gave rhamnetin and rhamnose (pc in EtOAc-pyridine-H₂O, 12:5:4 and EtOAc-PrOH-H₂O, 3:1:1). Methylation and acid hydrolysis gave 5,7,3',4'-tetramethoxyquercetin, identified by m.m.p. and co-chromatography with an authentic sample. 1 was methylated with Me₂SO₄ in aqueous NaOH and the methylated glycoside hydrolysed with 4N H₂SO₄. The partially methylated sugars were identified by pc (BuOH-EtOH-H₂O, 5:1:4).

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